

Job Satisfaction, Work Environment and Work Performance amongst Secondary School Teachers in the Central Region of Botswana

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine how the level of positions held by public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana influence their; salaries, job satisfaction, work environment, and promotion opportunities. The study was mainly quantitative and the positivist inquiry model was used, as a result, the data was collected using a questionnaire. The data was then analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and presented by means of inferential statistics by conducting One-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and One-Sample t-Tests. The study revealed that the level of positions held by public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana significantly influence their; salaries, job satisfaction, the work environment, and the promotion opportunities. The study, therefore, recommends that the government should review the teachers' salaries, offer an attractive salary scheme and introduce a flexible promotion policy.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Work environment, Promotion opportunities

Introduction

Teachers are regarded as a valuable asset to any nation around the globe. They, therefore, need to be highly recognized and given much credit for the remarkable job that they are doing just like any other profession. The former President of the United States of America, Barack Obama once advocated for teachers' recognition during the state of the Union address. He appreciated the teachers' contribution to the education of school going children. He said that teachers act as the children's parents, mentors as well as the nations' builders. He emphasized that teachers should be treasured and respected for the noble services that they render to learners since they face several challenges of which some are not easy to deal with (Pansiri & Bulawa, 2013).

When acknowledging President Obama's perception about teachers and their challenging job, Pansiri and Bulawa (2013) concurred with the idea that indeed teachers are valuable to any society and added that teachers can change the world. This is because teachers have the know-how and considerable professional intelligence and influence which can make and change learners into a particular society that they aspire to become. However, Most of the public secondary schools in Botswana were established many years ago but some have never been renovated while others have unsatisfactory refurbishment. This clearly indicates that teachers are not recognized and they are disgruntled by the poor working conditions which they say continuously hamper productivity, and this contributes to the poor results in most Botswana public secondary schools (Botswana Dailynews, 21 January 2016).

According to Wong (2004. p. 41), "Teachers hired today are the teachers for the next generation. So, their success determines the success of an entire generation". He further asserts that effective and experienced teachers are associated with greater student achievement. Therefore, if a school is to produce good results, it must also have a good workforce in the form of happy, motivated, respected, efficient and effective teachers. However, the teaching profession is faced with various problems. These are related to teachers' job satisfaction, inadequate promotion opportunities, unattractive salaries, and unsatisfactory working conditions. The common observation, therefore, is that teachers in government secondary schools, regardless of their positions, are dissatisfied with their profession.

Githinji (2014) explains that when teachers are promoted sufficiently, they are answerable to certain responsibilities that are related to their new positions and this develops them to become responsible officers. As such, they get motivated to do their best to improve their working places. On the other hand, Murage (2011) noted that the workers' likelihood for promotion positively influences their job satisfaction as teachers decide to enter the profession for different reasons. However, research indicates that all teachers share the need for appreciation, recognition, and development during their professional careers. MacBeath (2012), states that

research has shown that whenever teachers are asked about their priorities and satisfy in many developing countries worldwide, they refer to the importance of recognition and respect for their daily challenges as well as their accomplishments.

For teachers to be productive, their job needs to provide them with a level of satisfaction and some motivation. This is because all the employees join their workplaces to satisfy their personal needs. So, it is apparent that the working conditions and the salary of teachers should make them happy and inspire them to work hard so as to produce good results. Nevertheless, in cases where they are not satisfied, teachers tend not to do their best. As a result, their learners get poor academic results. Besides, the workers, including teachers, report to their work stations in order to satisfy their financial, social, and physiological needs in life. So, job satisfaction in the context of a teacher should embrace the ability of the teaching job to meet the needs of teachers in order to improve their job performance (Kituto, 2011).

It is further essential to note that the job satisfaction of teachers at all levels is a significant aspect in the workplace and has been linked with improved performance and increased dedication to the organisation. Kituto (2011) clarifies that keeping the morale of the workers high can be a remarkable achievement to any institution because a happy workforce would likely to be inspired to put much effort in their work and ultimately produce outstanding results, have less absenteeism and stay loyal to their organisation.

Despite that many researchers have advocated for teachers to be given a high professional position in the societies they live in to match their professional responsibilities, qualifications, and their contribution to the development of any society, teachers in many developing countries are not yet recognized. Many teachers have therefore resorted to leaving the profession and joining other organisations which they hope would value their worth by offering them satisfactory working conditions. However, the teachers that remain in the profession treat teaching as a stepping stone which they use to settle down while looking for greener pastures elsewhere. On the other hand, the unsatisfactory salaries force teachers to find part time jobs to augment the meager pay that they receive at the end of the month and this greatly affects their productivity (Tsayang, Monyatsi & Mhlauli, 2017).

The unsatisfactory working conditions of teachers in public secondary schools, unsatisfactory salaries, inadequate promotion opportunities, and the compromised job satisfaction have resulted in many teachers despising the profession as well as themselves. This has led to Botswana basic education facing various challenges. During the Botswana Sector of Educators' Trade Union (BOSETU) conference which was held in 2017 at Majestic Five hotel in Palapye, the President for the union; Mr. Modukanele stated that Botswana's basic education and secondary schooling, in particular, is facing several challenges. He cited dilapidated infrastructure, large school enrolments, unattractive salaries, housing shortages and lack of promotions as some of the major aspects which gravely demotivated teachers. In the midst of the countless challenges faced by the public secondary school teachers, the most outstanding one since 2007 according to Mr. Modukanele was the continual decline in the national examination results for public secondary school learners. The union president attributed the decline in public secondary schools performance to the fact that teachers' welfare is not taken into serious consideration. Hence, he pointed out that teachers do not exert much effort to their work and this affects the future of learners at the end (Tsayang, Monyatsi & Mhlauli, 2017).

When addressing teachers in Ghazni, in June 2018, the President of Botswana, His Excellency, Dr. Mokgweetsi Masisi admitted that many teachers in public secondary schools have not been promoted for too long and that some even left the profession without receiving any promotion. However, he said that as of April 1, 2019, the government had created 1754 positions for teachers and was currently absorbing the staff into those posts. He promised that the government would ensure that the secondary schools would be renovated and that learning resources would be availed to learners. In addition, the Minister of Basic Education, Mr. Bagalatia Arone stated that quality education cannot be attained without improved conditions of service for teachers. He emphasized that infrastructural challenges in secondary schools needed urgent attention. This is an indication that the government of Botswana is trying its best to satisfy teachers so as to resolve the issues which are associated with poor performance in public secondary schools (Dailynews, 2018).

Theoretical Background

Orodho (2009) defines a theoretical framework as a collection of interrelated ideas which are established from theories and attempt to explain why things are the way they are based on theories. A theoretical framework introduces the new views of the research problem and allows the understanding of the realm of the problem. In addition, Best and Khan (2008) state that a theoretical framework helps to conceptualize the topic in its entire state and acknowledges the problem from a wider perspective for objectivity purposes. In many fields, theories and suggestions about concepts and relationships have been formulated. In such fields, the researcher may be interested in finding out about a particular theory (Best & Khan, 2008).

This study was guided by Herzberg's two-factor theory, which is also referred to as motivator or hygiene theory, formulated by Fredrick Herzberg. Though for many years, the theory was widely used in industrial contexts, the two-factor theory has been mostly used in educational settings like educational management and classroom management (Erkilic, 2008). Herzberg (1966) studied some workers and then placed them into two groups of their state of motivation; 1) Motivation factors: those elements that contribute to good performance and lead to job satisfaction such as; achievement, recognition, work itself, advancement and responsibility. 2) The Hygiene factors; those factors that are not strong contributors to job satisfaction but must be present to meet workers' expectations and prevent job dissatisfaction such as; salary, security, fringe benefits, working conditions, position or status, interpersonal relation, and company policies.

Herzberg indicates that, for workers to be happy and motivated, managers must consider satisfying the intrinsic nature and the content of the job. They must give the employees the opportunity to be responsible through the use of promotions so that they gain some recognition and develop their skills and careers through accountability. He further states that there are certain factors in the workplace that cause job satisfaction, while a separate set of factors cause dissatisfaction. He mentions that the work factors such as; wages, job security, or advancement make people feel happy about their jobs. In most institutions and schools in particular, the school managers still need to deal away with those factors that promote job dissatisfaction so that teachers are satisfied to prevent unfavorable behaviors' among employees, which might lead to strikes, high labor turnover, gossip, frequent absenteeism and late coming for duty (Herzberg, 1966) .

In his research, Herzberg (1966) claims that when the hygiene factors are met, this does not mean that employees will be motivated. It is only if the motivator factors are met that an employee will be motivated. This means that even if the salaries of workers are increased, they will not be satisfied. However, they will be able to have what they need with the money that they have, but they will still not be happy with their jobs.

However, the absence of the hygiene factors does not give positive satisfaction results. So, if the hygiene factors do not meet the employees' expectations, the workers might be dissatisfied with their jobs. To enhance job satisfaction and motivate somebody to perform better, motivation factors need to be considered and then attended to. The Hygiene factors are necessary to make sure that an employee is not dissatisfied. As a result, to ensure that the job attitudes and productivity of workers are maintained, the public secondary schools' managers need to satisfy both the hygiene factors and the motivation factors so that they reduce job dissatisfaction amongst the workers (Erkilic, 2008).

Hertzberg's theory helps in learning the factors that bring about satisfaction and dissatisfaction in the life of a worker. Behind his theory and academic teachings, Hertzberg was basically attempting to bring more humanity and caring into the workplace. He wanted to clearly explain how people can be managed properly, for the good of all people at work. As such, Herzberg's research proved that people, and teachers inclusive, will do their best to achieve the "hygiene" needs because they are unhappy without them. However, once satisfied, the effect of the needs soon deteriorates as satisfaction is temporary (Mbongo, 2015). The researcher, therefore, wanted to find out the relevance of Herzberg's theory of motivation on how the level of positions held by teachers in the Central region of Botswana influence their salaries, job satisfaction, work environment, and promotion opportunities.

Problem and purpose

The continual deteriorating academic performance of public secondary school learners in Botswana is a worrisome factor to the citizens of Botswana, the Ministry of Basic Education and the government as a whole

(Moswela, 2014). Ever since the 2011 industrial strike, the public secondary school teachers have often been accused of not being committed to teaching learners proficiently and continuously producing unsatisfactory national examination results. During the past eight years, the Central region of Botswana has achieved poor academic results and this has been blamed on the government's failure to provide satisfactory working conditions mainly; attractive salaries, job satisfaction, satisfactory work environments and adequate promotion opportunities (BOSETU newsletter, 2017).

The Botswana Dailynews which was published on the 27 February 2018 pointed out that the public secondary school's results have declined over the years. During an interview, the permanent Secretary in the Ministry of Basic Education, Ms. Grace Muzila stated that this decline in secondary schools is further heightened by the huge numbers of students who are admitted into the secondary schools. This she said overwhelmed the teachers whose working conditions are not satisfactory. She said that the teacher student ratio is a serious issue which needs to be addressed (Botswana Dailynews, 2018). Therefore, it is clear that Botswana basic education is faced with several challenges which contribute towards unsatisfactory academic performance in public secondary schools.

On the other hand, Isaiah and Nenty (2012) indicate that it is essential to acknowledge that public secondary school teachers in Botswana are still unhappy despite all the government's attempts to satisfy them. It is therefore clear that teachers' low levels of motivation are worrisome as this was once even highlighted in the two National Commissions of Education (National Commissions of Education, 1997, 1993).

Thus, the purpose of this study was to investigate on how the level of positions held by public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana influence their; salaries, job satisfaction, work environment and promotion opportunities with the hope of coming up with some useful recommendations towards work performance among public secondary schools teachers.

Research questions

1. To what extent are teachers satisfied with their work-related behaviours?
2. Is there a relationship between the positions of secondary school teachers and their salaries, job satisfaction, promotion opportunities, and the work environment?

Research Hypotheses

H_{A1}: Teachers are significantly not satisfied with their salaries, job satisfaction, their work Environment and Promotion opportunities

H_{A2}: The designation of teachers has a significant influence on their Salaries, Job satisfaction, Work environment and Promotion opportunities

Literature review

The level of positions held by secondary school teachers and salary

An interesting question which is often asked with regard to salary is, "Does money stimulate an employee to put more effort? The answers to this question are always different depending on individual needs. Money is frequently referred to as "purchasing an end". Money plays a vital role in the employees' work performance as it enables them to satisfy their fundamental needs. As a result, workers are motivated by money to be productive than other means of motivation. Therefore, it is worth noting that money is important to employees despite their positions or the amount of the salaries they get. This is because money is mostly treasured worldwide. That is why teachers and any other workers go for industrial actions when they want their salaries to be increased (Adjei-Sefa, 2007).

When employees are motivated with attractive salaries, managers should clearly clarify that workers who exceed the set organisational performance targets will be appreciated with money. Those employees who go beyond the organisational targets should repeatedly be rewarded with money so that they continue to be efficient in their job. This agrees with Thorndike's proposed law of effect, which states that "actions followed by satisfying change or consequences are more likely to be repeated in situations on future occasions." Therefore, it is clear that the several strikes that teachers engage in are an indication that money has a significant influence on the employees' work related behaviour and performance.

According to Tang, Kim, and Tang (2000. p. 216) in Haines (2007), money is seen as the measure of value. "In America and around the world, money is how we keep score and the importance attached to money is one's motive to outperform others". Hoy and Miskel (1996) added that teachers get motivated when they are hopeful that they would earn more money if they perform well as the salaries they get do not meet their basic needs. So, regardless of the positions held by the public secondary school teachers, an attractive salary is a gateway to improved work performance. As such, both teachers in high and low positions need money to fulfill their needs. When such needs are met, teachers get motivated to do their level best in order to improve their work performance.

It is significant to consider that a salary is an essential aspect of job satisfaction and dissatisfaction of various employees and teachers in particular. Child (1984) speculates that even though it is commonly said that money cannot buy happiness, as a worldwide medium of exchange, money is evidently the key to many good things that are considered important and valuable to people.

The level of positions of secondary teachers and job satisfaction

Job satisfaction has a long history of the study. Iaffaldano and Muchinsky (1985) reveal that the study of the correlation between job satisfaction and work performance has a controversial history. The Hawthorne studies, conducted in the 1930s, are often commended for enlightening the researchers about the effects of employee attitudes on work performance. Hence, immediately after the findings of the Hawthorne studies, many researchers got fascinated by the concept - "a happy worker is a productive worker".

Peretomode (1991) explained that the higher the position of the job, the greater the job satisfaction. However, many workers are satisfied, even those in low paying jobs. It is clear therefore that, job satisfaction is mainly concerned with how someone feels about their job rather than the position that someone holds. On the other hand, Whawo (1993) indicated that job satisfaction can be influenced by different factors, including; the employee's relationship with the supervisor, the quality of the physical environment in which people work and the level of achievement in the workplace. Nevertheless, several researchers disagree that when people have high job satisfaction level, they achieve exceptional job performance. In fact, increased job satisfaction can sometimes reduce job performance.

Even so, Taylor (2007) pointed out that job satisfaction is derived from different circumstances and can be defined as "any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that cause a person to honestly say, 'I am satisfied with my job'." He further explains that job satisfaction completely depends on various factors which work together to provide the vital balance, which gives an employee some sense of satisfaction at work.

Kavanagh and Halpern (1977) discovered that public secondary school teachers who are in high-level positions such as Principal and Deputy Principals did not experience any greater satisfaction in their work lives because of their higher status and the responsibilities they held. They emphasize that teacher individual differences play a major role in the job satisfaction of public secondary school teachers than the positions held.

On the other hand, a survey was conducted amongst 164 assistant principals in southeastern Pennsylvania to determine the extent to which their positional tasks were related to their job satisfaction. The tasks that generated the highest degree of job satisfaction included: teacher evaluation, teacher supervision, and the preparation of the school's master schedule. The survey revealed that there is a strong relationship between job satisfaction and the limitation of task accountability, task value, and flexible authority (Garawski, 1977).

The 1970 research study by Austin and Brown established that many assistant principals were not happy in their positions as compared to their junior teachers. Some high level job satisfaction was commonly achieved by assistant principals whose hard work and commitment had been recognized and rewarded. However, the study further discovered that the assistant principals' low-satisfaction emanated from the attendance and student discipline tasks they were entrusted with since much of their work was controlled by rules without them being free to come up with their own initiatives and this hampered their progress to do more. The researchers also discovered that assistant principals mostly left their schools and joined other departments in order to get some recognition and motivation through better salaries and positions (Austin & Brown, 1970).

From the various studies on job satisfaction, Cunningham (2015) affirms that teachers in various positions in public secondary schools are dissatisfied and are therefore not committed to the teaching profession. This has resulted in poor learner academic performance in the national examinations across many developing countries worldwide. Nevertheless, Latham (1998, p. 83), points out that, “job satisfaction can do far more than help retain teachers; it can improve their teaching.” This means that if teachers are satisfied with their jobs, they tend to contribute significantly to the improvement of students’ academic performance and their schools’ efficiency.

Similarly, Shann (2001) confirms that job satisfaction can assist in keeping teachers and make them be focused and dedicated to their job, thereby making their schools very successful. In other words, job satisfaction plays a crucial role in the improvement of teaching, and learners’ academic results. Hence, job satisfaction has major institutional and managerial implications. If the job satisfaction is high, the employees will perform better. But, if the job satisfaction is low, there will be performance problems. As a result, satisfaction causes good performance in teachers of varied positions.

The positions held by public secondary teachers and the work environment

The work environment of every employee influences works performance. The work environment encompasses all the processes, systems, structures, tools and conditions that are found in the workplace that affect an employee’s work performance. The school policies, school rules, organisational culture, working relations as well as both the internal and external environmental factors are some of the work environment aspects which contribute to how teachers perform their job. As such, the work environment offers a platform on which work is done. It is worth noting, therefore, to point out that public secondary school teachers in various positions within the schools should be provided with a satisfactory work environment for them to execute their duties effectively and efficiently (Olango, 2011).

The work environment that makes up a particular school influences the level at which its workers perform. Maicibi (2005) asserts that the management of public secondary schools should control the work environment appropriately in order to improve the employees’ job satisfaction and productivity. He further points out that the work environment of any organisation and schools inclusive should play a vital role in enhancing the employees’ work performance and job satisfaction. This is because the responsibilities that are performed by workers in contemporary offices are based on complicated technology. Therefore, organisations should ensure that their employees are not unfavorably affected by such an environment.

In 2011, Kreitner and Kinicki discussed the Hawthorne effect and discovered a significant correlation between the working conditions of the employees’ and their effectiveness. The results of the Hawthorne studies experiment revealed a strong connection between the work performance of workers and their surroundings as well as the people they are working with. Within a certain working environment, some observations have shown that outgoing and supportive core-workers have a great influence on improved job satisfaction and this eventually results in good work performance (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2011).

Where teachers are subjected to working in poor work environments, whether in high or low positions, they tend not to be free in their workplaces. So, they would find some means of escaping from the horrible situations they are facing. As such, when the slightest opportunity comes their way, they leave the schools forever and find some work where the conditions of work are satisfactory. As a result, the work environment for public secondary school teachers is fundamental to how employees feel about their workplace. Besides, when the environment of an institution is favorable and pleasant to them, the employees will feel proud about it. In several workplaces, the employees derive their personal comfort from a favorable work environment so that they perform their duties diligently and effectively in order to produce good results. Therefore, when employees are provided with a satisfactory work environment, they perform to their level best; remain committed and interested in the job, thus achieving great organisational outcomes (Musazi, 2003).

When teachers work in satisfactory working environments, they often have good relationships amongst themselves and learners. As a result, the teachers in good working conditions get motivated and have high job satisfaction level. However, the classes with high numbers of learners, unreasonable workloads for both teachers and the school management coupled with hostile relationships within the school demoralize teachers and stifle their motivation. This further weakens the teachers’ commitment to the job (Mathew, 2005).

Therefore, it is evident that the literature shows a strong link between the work environment and public secondary school teachers' work performance. Demet (2012) emphasizes that people who work under undesirable conditions may end up with low work performance and can face occupational health diseases which further causes high absenteeism and turnover.

The level of positions of teachers and promotion opportunities

Teachers are extremely motivated when their efforts are recognized through promotions at reasonable spaces of time in the teaching service. This is because they will be unhappy if they remain in the same positions for a long time. Nyakondo (2015) explains that promotions are in different forms. They range from raising a salary, getting an elevated job or basically being moved to a higher position within an organisational set up. Nzuve (2010) on the contrary, describes promotion as a transfer from a job at a lower level to another at a higher level within the organisation. It is the way of enhancing an employee's position with more duties and responsibilities as well as improved salary and higher status.

Generally, many people treat some promotions as good opportunities in which they gain more benefits both financially and non-financially. By obtaining higher positions, promoted workers have more chances to articulate and widen their potential which in turn provides them with more motivation to execute their daily duties even better. Besides, promotions can be used as a form of compensation to motivate employees. As a result, the end product of promotions may differ in various organisations and the workers' age since different employees have different perceptions about promotions. Some may be motivated to work hard so as to receive a promotion while others may not be interested in being promoted. While the junior teachers will be inspired to do their best in order to get a higher position in the school, the senior teachers will also be motivated to work towards getting an even higher post as well (Mary-Jane, n.d).

After getting a promotion, there is more work that an employee is obliged to do. He or she is expected to be more accountable to all the responsibilities entrusted on him by the organisation. If the employee puts more effort into his work, performing all the expected duties beyond the expectations, such worker deserves to be promoted. Therefore, the employer or the supervisor should further elevate such worker on the basis of excellence. Besides, a promotion in many cases shows that the employee is ready to be given extra accountability in the organisation and is established enough to carry out even bigger roles within the workplace (Mary-Jane, n.d).

Exceptional performance emanates from working hard and being dedicated to working, then this later leads to promotion. Savych (2005) indicates that promotion levels are used as delayed compensation because of approximately all junior workers; and teachers inclusive, have to prove themselves before they are promoted. The hope of being promoted inspires the good workers to do their best so as to be elevated as well. In other situations, promotion opportunities could motivate employees through improved salaries or income, particularly in competitive environments. The reputation that is gained from a higher position rather than a higher salary encourages some employees to work hard so that they win the competition. As a result, promotion should be regarded as a lasting motivation that is more efficient in employees with stable jobs, such as teachers in secondary schools especially those who seldom change jobs. In Botswana, both in government and non-government organizations, promotion opportunities are considered very important by many employees, because they give the promoted employees more accountability in the areas they have been promoted to (Kiyoshi, 2006).

Murage (2003) asserts that deferred promotion to Headship for Deputy Principals could be a cause of dissatisfaction in them. As a result, her study findings recommend that the Deputy principals with a Master of Education should be well remunerated and promoted to headship in order to prevent them from leaving the education sector for better-paying jobs. Therefore, Njue (2003) placed promotion as number three insignificance so as to promote job satisfaction and improve the employees' work performance.

Methodology

A quantitative approach was deemed most suitable to examine the relationship between gender, designation, and work related behavior amongst the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana. The approach was decided upon mainly because the research employed a questionnaire which allowed the

researcher to include as many teachers as possible so as to collect standardized information from the respondents, making generalizability possible, and then general trends relating to gender, designation and work related behavior amongst the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana were easily identified. Leedy (1993, p.144) emphasizes that “A quantitative approach focuses on consistent and objective data, and uses highly structured procedures designed to verify or disprove predetermined hypotheses”.

In addition, this was an inferential survey which used a questionnaire as the basis of the study. So, this study targeted teachers in the Department of Public Service Management (DPSM) payroll who were deployed to teach in Public Secondary schools in the Central region of Botswana. The teachers were from both Junior and Senior Secondary Schools which are geographically spread. From the ten schools understudy, the population comprised of 680 teachers, as according to the provided school records obtained from the concerned schools and the report from the Central region (Ministry of Education, n.d). The 420 teachers were from the Senior Secondary schools while 260 were from Junior Secondary schools. However, the target population consisted of 313 males of which 167 were from senior secondary schools while 146 from junior secondary schools in the region. The 367 females comprised 198 teachers from junior secondary schools and 169 from senior secondary school in the region. Kasomo (2007) as cited in Nyange (2013) recommends the use of the largest sample possible as a calculation from a large sample is more correct than the one from a smaller sample. As a result, for accuracy purposes, the researcher used a larger sample in order to obtain reliable results. The sample size was, therefore, 32% of the population giving a sample of 213 respondents from the 10 secondary schools. The instrument’s reliability was established using cronbach alpha estimates after trial testing and all the variables had an internal consistency index above .80.

Data analysis and interpretation of results

H₀₁: The secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana:

- *Are significantly dissatisfied with their salaries*
- *are not significantly satisfied with their job*
- *are significantly not satisfied with their work environment*
- *have a significant lack of promotion opportunities*

This hypothesis was tested by carrying out five population t-test analysis of secondary school teachers responses to (i) an item “salaries” designed to measure the level to which teachers’ salaries influence their work related behavior; (ii) Teachers’ level of job satisfaction influence their work related behaviour; (iii) The level to which the teachers’ work environment influence their work related behavior; and (iv) Teachers’ level of promotion opportunities influence their work related behavior.

For each of the four variables using SPSS computer package, the analysis statistically compared observed mean with the expected mean as presented in Table 1.

Table 1

One Sample t-Test Analysis of the Level to which Teachers’ Salaries, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Promotion Opportunities, and In-service Training Influence Work Related Behaviour.

Variable	μ	\bar{X}	SD	Mean Diff	t-value	Sig
Salaries	10.5	8.41	3.54	-2.09	-7.33	.000
Job satisfaction	17.5	18.53	5.33	1.02	2.39	.018
Work performance	14	5.00	2.82	-9.00	-39.58	.000
Promotion Opportunities	7	5.00	2.82	-2.00	-8.80	.000

$p < .05$ (2-tailed).

Regarding teachers' perceptions on the salaries they receive, this resulted in a negative t-value of -7.33 which was found to be significant at .05 alpha level. The null hypothesis has been retained. This, therefore, means that, in the perception of the public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana, there are significantly not satisfied with their salaries. As for job satisfaction in connection with teachers' work performance, the t-value obtained was 2.39. This was found higher than the critical t-value of 1.96. Hence, the null hypothesis was still retained. This then revealed that teachers in the Central region secondary schools are not satisfied with their job.

Furthermore, the teachers' view of their work environment with regard to their work performance as shown in Table 1 above, at- the value of -39.58 given was realised to be significant at .05 alpha level. This then meant that the null hypothesis was retained. As a result, this indicated that the secondary school teachers in the Central region were not happy with their work environment.

Based on the collected data on promotion opportunities, the negative t-value of -8.80 was found to be significant at the 0.5 alpha level. The results led to the null hypothesis being retained, which then indicated that the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana stated that they lack promotion opportunities.

H₀₃: The level of positions held by public secondary school teachers in the Central region has no significant influence on their Salaries, Job Satisfaction, The Work Environment, and Promotion Opportunities

In testing this hypothesis, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out to establish how the positions held by the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana influence their perception on their salaries, job satisfaction, work environment, promotion opportunities, and in-service training (see Table 2).

Regarding the teachers' perception of salaries, the analysis gave an F-value of 8.47 with a 4 and 149 degrees of freedom. This was found to indicate a significant influence beyond .05 alpha level. As a result, the null hypothesis was retained. As for the teachers' perception of job satisfaction in connection with their work performance, an F-value of 8.78 with 4 and 149 degrees of freedom. This, therefore, shows that there is a significant influence that is beyond .05 alpha level which leads to the retaining of the null hypothesis.

Concerning the teachers' perception of their work environment with regard to their work related behavior, the results provided an F-value of 3.85 with a 4 and 149 degrees of freedom. This further revealed a significant influence that is beyond the .05 alpha level. This also led to the null hypothesis being retained. As for the Central region secondary school teachers' perception of promotion opportunities, the findings indicated an F-value of 8.78 with a 4 and 149 degrees of freedom. The results reveal a significant influence that is beyond the .05 alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was further retained.

Table 2

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the Influence of Level of teachers' positions (LOP) On Salaries, Job Satisfaction, The Work environment and Promotion Opportunities in Secondary Schools In the Central Region of Botswana.

Variable	LOP	n	\bar{X}	SD	Source of variation	SS	Df	ms	F	Sig
Salaries	S/ Head	11	12.82	2.56	Between Groups	355.08	4	88.77	8.47	.000
	Head Of Dept	14	10.07	3.81						
	Snr Teacher I	26	7.38	2.87	Within Groups	1562.15	149	10.49		
	Snr Teacher II	95	7.76	3.33						
	Ass Teacher	8	10.52	2.88						
	TOTAL	154	8.41	3.54						
				TOTAL	1917.23	153				
Job satisfaction	S/Head	11	22.73	2.76	Between Groups	406.25	4	101.56	8.78	.005
	Head Of Dept	14	20.93	3.71						
	Snr Teacher I	26	17.62	6.41	Within Groups	3939.15	149	26.40		
	Snr Teacher II	95	17.73	5.18						
	Ass Teacher	8	21.00	4.31						
	TOTAL	154	18.53	5.33						
				TOTAL	4340.40	153				
Work environment	S/Head	11	8.18	3.03	Between Groups	232.24	4	58.06	3.85	.000
	Head Of Dept	14	6.64	3.15						
	Snr Teacher I	26	4.50	2.64	Within Groups	985.76	149	6.62		
	Snr Teacher II	95	4.35	2.45						
	Ass Teacher	8	7.13	1.89						
	TOTAL	154	5.00	2.82						
				TOTAL	1218.00	153				
Promotion opportunities	S/Head	11	8.18	3.03	Between Groups	232.24	4	58.06	8.78	.000
	Head Of Dept	14	6.64	3.15						
	Snr Teacher I	26	4.50	2.64	Within Groups	985.76	149	6.62		
	Snr Teacher II	95	4.35	2.45						
	Ass Teacher	8	7.13	1.89						
	TOTAL	154	5.00	2.82						
				TOTAL	1218.00	153				

A closer look at Table 3 shows that the positions held by the secondary school teachers in Central region of Botswana significantly influence their; better salaries, job satisfaction, work environment, promotion opportunities, and in-service training.

When this trend was tested statistically using Fisher's Least Significance Difference (LSD) test, it was found that the School Heads are the least satisfied with their salaries ($M=12.82$) than the Senior Teacher I teachers ($M=7.38$). The School Heads, therefore, indicate that they do not receive satisfactory salaries when compared to the Senior Teacher I teachers.

With regard to job satisfaction, the School Heads were still found to be the least satisfied with their job when compared to the Senior Teacher II teachers. This is revealed by the School Heads Mean of 22.73 as compared to the Senior Teacher II teachers' Mean of 17.62. This further showed that the School Heads are not satisfied with their jobs.

Concerning the work environment, in correlation with the teachers' positions, the School Heads still showed that they were the least contented with the work environment. The findings indicated their Mean of 8.8

in comparison to the Senior Teacher II teachers' Mean of 4.35. The results showed that the School Heads were the least content with the work environment in their schools.

Furthermore, regarding the promotion opportunities, the School Heads (M= 8.18) as compared to the Senior Teachers II teachers (M=4.35) further revealed them as the least satisfied with promotion opportunities. The findings significantly indicated that the School Heads do not have promotion opportunities (See Table 3).

Table 3

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on how the Level of Teachers' Positions (LOP) significantly influence their; Salaries, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, and Promotion Opportunities Among Secondary School Teachers In the Central Region of Botswana.

Variable	LOP	N	Mean
Salaries	School Head	11	12.82
	Head of Department	14	10.07
	Senior Teacher I	26	7.38
	Senior Teacher II	95	7.76
	Assistant Teacher	8	10.50
	TOTAL	54	8.41
Job satisfaction	School Head	11	22.73
	Head of Department	14	20.93
	Senior Teacher I	26	17.62
	Senior Teacher II	95	17.73
	Assistant Teacher	8	21.00
	TOTAL	54	18.53
Work environment	School Head	11	8.18
	Head of Department	14	6.64
	Senior Teacher I	26	4.50
	Senior Teacher II	95	4.35
	Assistant Teacher	8	7.13
	TOTAL	54	5.00
Promotion opportunities	School Head	11	8.18
	Head of Department	14	6.64
	Senior Teacher I	26	4.50
	Senior Teacher II	95	4.35
	Assistant Teacher	8	7.13
	TOTAL	54	5.00

Summary of the findings

Positions held by the secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana significantly influence their; salaries, job satisfaction, work environment, and promotion opportunities.

School Heads come out as the least satisfied officers clearly showing that they are not necessarily happy with their job. Teachers indicated a significant lack of promotion opportunities.

Discussions, Conclusions, and recommendations

Discussions

The findings of this study showed a strong connection between the positions held by secondary teachers and their salaries, job satisfaction, the work environment, and promotion opportunities. The findings revealed that the public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana, regardless of their positions within the schools, are not happy with the salaries that they are given and this seriously affects how they deliver their daily duties. The BOSETU newsletter (2017) supports this by confirming that the unsatisfactory performance in

public secondary schools in Botswana is attributed to the teachers' unattractive salaries and inadequate promotion opportunities.

Muguongo, Muguna, and Muriithi (2015) concur with the findings of this study that teachers' salaries are strongly related to their work performance despite the positions that they hold in different schools. They explain that money is essential in ensuring that individuals' needs are fulfilled. As such, when salaries are attractive and match the job demands, individuals' skills and pay standards, employees' job satisfaction is enhanced and this improves the work performance of the workers. This is also supported by a study by Adjei-Sefa which was conducted in 2007. The findings of the study indicate that many workers are inspired by an attractive salary to work to their best regardless of their positions in the organisation or the amount of money that they receive. Therefore, it is not surprising when public secondary school teachers go on strikes for salary increase because money is the only medium used to meet people's basic needs and wants.

Moreover, this study revealed that public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana are not happy with their job. These findings are a truthful manifestation of what is currently happening in most schools in the Central region of Botswana. The fact that many teachers have part time jobs in addition to their full time work is a clear indication that they are not satisfied with the conditions of their job and their salaries in particular. To support the findings of this study, Muguongo et al (2015) explain that job satisfaction and teachers' work performance are closely related. They indicate that if workers are highly satisfied with their jobs, they tend to do their best in order to improve the performance of their workplaces.

Despite that this study revealed a strong relationship between the teachers' job satisfaction and work performance, Luthans (2002) disagrees and states that there is no connection between job satisfaction and performance. He articulates that job satisfaction does not automatically result in good performance. However, he points out that in the previous research, a very low average of 0.17 was found to translate the connection between job satisfaction and work performance. As a result, he declares that it does not mean that if employees are happy with their work, they will perform well. He, therefore, cites other factors such as fear to be dismissed from work as the other aspect which might compel workers to work hard and achieve good results apart from job satisfaction.

The findings of this study further revealed that public secondary school teachers in the Central region of Botswana are not pleased with their work environment. Thus, a strong relationship between the teachers work environment and work performance has been established. Various literature findings support the results of this study and stress that the work environment and the behavior of the employees are strongly related. Muguongo et al (2015) concur with this study's findings. They established that the work environment and the teachers' work performance are strongly related. The conclusion drawn from their research was that a favorable work environment has a positive influence on the teachers' work related behaviour which eventually improves their work performance.

In addition, this study established that the School Heads in public secondary schools in the Central region of Botswana are the least happy with their work environment. This is because as the drivers of the schools and the school management as a whole, the school Heads make sure that the schools run smoothly despite the challenges they meet within the different school environments. In support of these findings, Conjoh, Taylor-Morgan, Sesay, Mbayo and Sesay (2017) indicate that the School Heads in public secondary schools in South Eastern Pennsylvania were the least happy with their work environment when compared to other teachers in their schools, particularly the senior teachers.

Furthermore, this study discovered a strong connection between the promotion opportunities of public secondary schools in the Central region of Botswana and their work performance. The teachers are not happy because some have never been promoted ever since their first posts while others have been in certain senior posts for too long and this negatively affects how they perform their teaching duties. Haines (2007) supports the findings of this research. He reveals that promotions influence the work performance of public secondary teachers. His survey among the public secondary school teachers discovered that they were not happy with the level at which they were promoted. However, the study considerably pointed out that the School Heads have limited promotion opportunities than other teachers in the schools. The main reason given was that School

Heads are in the highest positions unlike those teachers in lower positions who can still be considered for promotion at any time.

Recommendations

- The government should renovate the entire secondary school's infrastructure in order to improve the working conditions of the schools in the Central Region.
- The government should review the current salaries for teachers and offer an attractive salary scheme for all secondary school teachers.
- The government should assess the promotion policy for teachers and introduce the one with flexible terms.
- It is also recommended for further studies to other researchers to carry out a qualitative research to investigate on how the work environment impact the work performance of the secondary school teachers across all positions in Botswana.

References

- i. Adjei-Sefa, G. (2007). *Employee Motivation and Productivity in three private Organisations in Accra, Unpublished Master thesis, University of Coast, Cape Coast.*
- ii. Austin, D. B., & Brown, H. L. (1970). *Report of the assistant principalship. Reston, VA: National Association of Secondary School Principals.*
- iii. Best, J. W. & Khan J. V. (1993). *Research in Education. Boston: Edward Arnold.*
- iv. BOSETU Conference, Majestic hotel, Palapye-held on 25 August, 2017.
- v. BOSETU Official Newsletter, 1/2017.
- vi. Botswana Dailynews, January, 2016.
- vii. Botswana Dailynews, June 2018, Gaborone.
- viii. Child, J. (1984). *Organisations - a guide to problems and practices: 2nd Edition. New York, Harper & Row.*
- ix. Conjoh, A. M., Taylor-Morgan, E. M., Sesay, I., Mbayo, K., & Sesay, S. (2017). *School Administrators' and Teachers' Perceptions of Job Satisfaction & Job Performance in some secondary schools in Freetown, Sierra Leone: The Social Sciences, 12(6), 1340-1370.*
- x. Cunningham, S. L. (2015). *A quantitative Analysis of the factors associated with teacher attrition and perceptions towards job satisfaction: Seton Hall University Dissertations and theses.*
- xi. Demet, L. (2012). *Impact of workplace quality on employee's productivity: A case study of a bank in turkey: Journal of Business, Economic & Finance, 1(1).*
- xii. Erkilic, T. A. (2008). *A discussion on the application of the Two Factor X and Y theories in Classroom management: American Journal of Scientific Research, 3(1), 111-116.*
- xiii. Garawski, R. A. (1977). *The assistant principal: His job satisfaction, and organizational Potency, The Clearing House, 52(1), 8-10.*
- xiv. Githinji, E. W. (2014). *Determinants of Deputy Principals' job satisfaction in public Secondary schools in Limuru district, Kenya, University of Nairobi; Masters thesis.*
- xv. Haines, A. G. (2007). *Job Satisfaction among high school principals in Mississippi. The University of Southern Mississippi: PhD dissertation.*
- xvi. Herzberg, F. (1966). *Work and the nature of man. Cleveland: World Publishing Company.*
- xvii. Hoy, W. K. & Miskel, C.G. (1996). *Educational administration: Theory, research, and Practice, 5th Edition. New York: McGraw - Hill.*
- xviii. Iaffaldano, M., T., & Muchinsky, P. M. (1985). *Job satisfaction and job performance: A Meta analysis. Psychological Bulletin, 97, 251-273.*
- xix. Isaiah, M., N., & Nenty, H. J. (2012). *Predicting Job Dissatisfaction among Community Junior Secondary School Teachers in Botswana: Scientific Research Journal, University of Botswana, Gaborone, 3 (3), 277 - 283.*

- xx. Kavanagh, M. J., & Halpern, M. (1977). *The impact of job level and sex differences on the relationship between life and job satisfaction*. *Academy of Management journal*, 20, 66-73.
- xxi. Kituto, H. M. (2011). *Factors that influence Job Satisfaction among teaching staff in large Public Secondary schools in Nairobi County: University of Nairobi*, 1(1).
- xxii. Kiyoshi, T. (2006). *Effects of wage and promotion incentives on the motivation levels of Japanese employees*, 11(3), 1-15.
- xxiii. Kreitner, R., & Kinick, A. (2011). *Organisational Behaviour*, McGraw Hill Irwin, New York.
- xxiv. Latham, A. (1998). *Teacher satisfaction*. *Association of Supervision and Curriculum Development*, 1(1), 82-83.
- xxv. Leedy, P. D. (1993). *Practical Research: Planning and Design*. 5th Edition: Macmillan Publishing Company, New York.
- xxvi. Luthans, F. (2005). *Organisational behaviour (10th Ed)* New York: McGraw Hill.
- xxvii. MacBeath, J. (2012). *The Future of the Teaching Profession*. Brussels: Education International.
- xxviii. Maicibi, N. A. (2005). *Introduction to Human Resource Management, (1st Ed.)*, Publication, Kampala.
- xxix. Mary, J. (n.d). *Employee Promotion & Performance Appraisal*, eHow. Retrieved from http://www.ehow.com/info_7864603_Employee-Promotion-Performance-appraisal.html.
- xxx. Mathew, L. J. (2005). *The impact of higher salaries and performance-related pay on retention rate of graduate teachers of public schools in Singapore: Faculty Education*, Monash University.
- xxxi. Mbongo, G. (2015). *The influence of the work environment on Job Satisfaction among Teachers in public schools in the Nembure Division, Embu West District, Kenya*, 3(1), 14-16.
- xxxii. Moswela, B. (2014). *Students' Academic Achievement: Whose Responsibility and Accountability: International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(10).
- xxxiii. Muguongo, M. M., Muguna, A. T., & Muriithi, D. K. (2015). *Effects of Compensation on Job Satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Maara Sub-County of Tharaka Nithi County, Kenya: Journal of Human Resource Management*. 1(6),47-59.
- xxxiv. Murage, A.W. (2003). *Job satisfaction among deputy head teachers of public secondary schools in Nairobi province*. M.Ed University of Nairobi.
- xxxv. Murage, S.W. (2011). *Teachers and school factors related to graduate teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Mombasa District Kenya, PhD Thesis,University of Nairobi*. PhD Thesis, University of Nairobi.
- xxxvi. Musazi, J. C. (2006). *The theory and practice of educational administration (1st Ed.)*, London and Oxford: Macmillan Education Ltd.
- xxxvii. Njue, C.W. (2003). *Job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Nairobi Province, Unpublished research project, University of Nairobi*.
- xxxviii. Nyakondo, O., H. (2015). *Influence of motivation on teachers' job performance in Public Secondary Schools in Kachuonyio South Sub- country, Homa-Bay County, Kenya: Kenyatta University*, 1(1), 9-34.
- xxxix. Nyange, M. N. (2013). *Factors influencing teachers' job satisfaction in Public secondary schools' in Voi district, Kenya, University of Nairobi*, 30 - 35
- xl. Nzuve, S.N. (2010). *Management of human resources. A Kenyan perspective (revised 4th Ed.)*, Nairobi: Tech and Pro Associates.
- xli. Olango, O. (2011). *Factors Influencing Employee Productivity in the Informal industry sector in a case of the EPZ, Nairobi*, 1(1).
- xlii. Orodho, J. A. (2004). *Essential of Educational and Social Science, Research methods*, Nairobi: Masola Publishers.
- xliii. Pansiri, N. O., & Bulawa, P. (2013). *An analysis of teachers' status in crisis of Public Service reforms in Botswana: European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 1(12), 233-244.
- xliv. Peretomode, V. F. (1991). *Educational Administration: Applied Concepts and Theoretical Perspective*, Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publishers.

- xlvi. Republic of Botswana. (1997). *Report of the National Commission on Education: Education for Kagisano (Social Harmony)*. Gaborone: Government Printers.
- xlvi. Republic of Botswana. (1993). *Report of the National Commission on Education of 1993*. Gaborone: Government Printers.
- xlvi. Savych, B. (2005). *Toward Incentives for Military Transformation A Review of Economic Models of Compensation*. Santa Monica: Rand Corporation. Retrieved From: http://www.rand.org/pubs/technical_reports/2005/RAND_TR194.pdf.
- xlvi. Shann, M. H. (2001). *Professional Commitment and Satisfaction among Teachers in Urban Middle schools*. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 9(2), 67- 73.
- xlvi. Tang, T. L., Kim, J. K., & Tang, D. S. (2000). *Does attitude toward money moderate the relationship between intrinsic job satisfaction and voluntary turnover*. *Human Relations*, 52(2), 213 - 245.
- l. Taylor, J. R. (2007). *Job satisfaction among High school assistants principals in seven Florida Counties: Graduate theses and Dissertations*.
- li. *The Patriot Newspaper*, March, 1, 2016, extracted from: editor@thepatriot.co.bw
- lii. Tsayang, G., Monyatsi, P. P., & Mhlauli, M. B. (2017). *Potentials for the Botswana Basic Education: Lessons from Shanghai Basic Education: University of Botswana*. 8(2), 142 - 156.
- liii. Wong, H. K. (2004). *Induction programs that keep new teachers teaching and improving*. *NASSP Bulletin*, 88(638), 41-58.
- liv. Whawo, D. D. (1993). *Educational Administration: Planning and Supervision*. Benin City: Jodah Publications.